

Hypotheses

H1: Goal-modelling benefits are perceived by those using GO-Plan

H1.1: Those using GO-Plan notice that they can better communicate about the FAIRification domain

H1.2: Those using GO-Plan notice that they can better understand the FAIRification domain

H1.3: Those using GO-Plan notice that they can better define the FAIRification scope

H1.4: Those using GO-Plan notice that they can better perform a FAIRification requirements elicitation

H1.5: Those using GO-Plan notice that they can improve the requirements elicited for FAIRification

H1.6: Those using GO-Plan notice that they can better design a FAIRification plan

H2: GO-Plan is perceived as easy to use by its users

H3: GO-Plan is perceived as useful by its users

H4: The users' perception of GO-Plan's ease of use positively affects their attitude towards using the method

H5: The users' perception of GO-Plan's usefulness positively affects their attitude towards using the method

H6: The users' positive attitude towards using GO-Plan will have an impact in determining their behavioural intention to use it.

Adapted TAM Framework

Questionnaire

Dear workshop participant,

Thank you for your time spent working on the use case. Below are a few questions about your impression of GO-Plan, which you just used. Please take a few minutes to answer the questions below. When assessing the statements, please think of your own professional practice.

Disclaimer:

The research team will collect and analyse the data but your responses will remain confidential, and no names will be included in any reports. The data collected during the study will be anonymous and treated following the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) privacy and security law.

By providing your consent you declare: (1) I am at least 18 years old, (2) I have read and I understand the provided information, (3) I freely and voluntarily consent to participate in this study, and (4) I comprehend that the responses gathered within this questionnaire will undergo analysis, and the findings of this analysis may be disseminated in a scholarly journal.

ID	Question	Related Hypoth.	Response Type
1	Learning about dog adoption helped me to communicate with other team members about this topic.	H1.1	Likert
2	Learning about FAIR and FAIRification helped me to communicate with other team members about this topic.	H1.1	Likert
3	The project description and its goals helped me to describe the domain of dog adoption.	H1.2	Likert
4	The description of the dog adoption domain helped me to identify semantic types about the topic.	H1.2	Likert
5	The list of semantic types helped me to identify potential reuse stakeholders.	H1.3	Likert
6	The list of reuse stakeholders helped me to	H1.3	Likert

	identify situations where others will reuse the data.		
7	The semantic types helped me to develop competency questions about dog adoption.	H1.4	Likert
8	The competency questions helped me to identify objectives of each collaborator.	H1.4	Likert
9	The objectives identified for the FAIRification project helped me to identify which FAIR principles to focus on.	H1.5	Likert
10	The prioritised goals helped me to define appropriate solutions for FAIRification.	H1.6	Likert
11	The tasks defined for the prioritised goals helped me to identify which metadata concepts should be collected about dog adoption.	H1.6	Likert
12	The tasks defined for the prioritised goals helped me to identify which expertise is needed in the FAIRification project.	H1.6	Likert
13	Are there other characteristics of GO-Plan that you think that would impact your resulting models when creating a FAIRification plan?	-	Open
14	On average, how many FAIRification projects have you participated in?	-	Open (numbers only)
15	In general, what role have you played in these projects?	-	Multiple Choice: 1. Ontologist, conceptual modeller 2. Project manager/leader 3. Linked data specialist 4. Domain Expert 5. Other (inform)
16	How confident are you in realising FAIRification?	-	Likert: <i>not confident to completely confident.</i>

17	Overall, I found the GO-Plan method easy to use.	H2	Likert
18	I have no difficulty understanding GO-Plan's tasks.	H2	Likert
19	The presence of someone with experience of FAIRification projects makes it easier for the team to use GO-Plan.	-	Likert
20	I think the method is useful as a source of knowledge to learn about FAIR and FAIRification.	H3	Likert
21	I think that GO-Plan is comprehensive about FAIRification.	H3	Likert
22	I am willing to use GO-Plan in my FAIRification projects in the future because I find the method easy to use.	H4	Likert
23	I am willing to use GO-Plan in my FAIRification projects in the future because I think it helped me to produce a robust FAIRification plan. <i>Robust: aligned with the main project requirements and constraints, clear and comprehensive.</i>	H5	Likert
24	If I participate in FAIRification projects in the future, I will use GO-Plan in these projects or I will suggest it to other people.	H6	Likert
25	What did you like the most about using GO-Plan for FAIRification planning?	-	Open
26	What did you like the least about using GO-Plan for FAIRification planning?	-	Open
27	What, if anything, positively surprised you about using GO-Plan?	-	Open
28	What, if anything, caused you frustration about using GO-Plan?	-	Open